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The effect of teacher's education on effectiveness of Physical Education lesson

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Abstract: The purpose of the present research was determining of the effect of teaching on effectiveness of physical education lesson in primary schools. The method of this research was semi-experimental. Three groups of primary school teachers participated in an education program before-designed voluntarily. Statistical population was including total of teachers of physical education first, second and threes in primary school teaching organization Tehran city. The method of sampling to selecting scope of teaching and primary schools was in hand and statistical sample was used non- random sample voluntary. In this research, data was collected by two styles, observation and interview. The first style was informed by writing spent time for variety activities of physical education lesson in primary and the second style informed to perception of teacher beliefs about teachers teaching program and perception of that teaching situation and also perception of students beliefs about of physical education lesson by interviewing. The results showed that increasing of participation students in class activities and decreasing of non- active time.

Keywords: Teaching, Effectiveness, Physical Education, Teacher, Student, Primary, In-Services teaching

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